

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Ochildiyeva Hilola G'ulomovna

POSSIBILITIES OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL

STUDENTS THROUGH MOVING GAMES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

TAQDIRLANADI

zenodo

2023/IYUN

